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Review Article

Review on Diabetes Mellitus and Study the Combination Effect of Dapagliflozin, Sitagliptin and Metformin

Sagar Kapil*¹, Neetika Kaushik²

¹ Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Dehradun

² Hari College of Pharmacy, Saharanpur

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ABSTRACT

Persistent Hyperglycemia brought on by an insulin secretion deficiency, insulin resistance, or both is an indication of diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic disease. It encompasses two primary types; Type 1 diabetes (T1D), primarily affecting children and resulting from autoimmune destruction of pancreatic beta cell, and Type 2 diabetes (T2D), which is more prevalent in adults and linked to lifestyle factor. The global prevalence of diabetes is rising, leading to microvascular and macrovascular complication, necessitating effective management strategies and intervention to mitigate its health and economic impacts. The use of Nanoparticle enhance the stability and bioavailability of insulin and other hypoglycemic agents, allowing for non-invasive administration like oral and pulmonary method, which improve patient compliance compared to traditional injection. Basically, nanoparticle based on lipid and polymeric formulation, have been developed to protect insulin from degradation in the gastrointestinal tract and ensure targeted delivery. Biguanide along combination with DPP-4 inhibitor and SGLT-2 inhibitor administered orally have good therapeutic action. The main goal in this article is to focus on lifestyle factor and mechanism involve in diabetes mellitus and study the therapeutic effect of combination of biguanide, DPP-4 inhibitor and SGLT-2 on diabetes.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a long-term metabolic condition and was first documented by an Egyptian and was founded a symptoms like weight reduction and polyuria. It was a Greek Physician Aertaeus who

coined term Diabetes Mellitus, in which 'Diabetes' means 'to pass through' and 'mellitus' which relate the Latin term 'honey.' (1). Over past years, various studied have been attempt to know about the spreadness of diseases, Moreover Previous studied have been done with multiple

*Corresponding Author: Sagar Kapil

Address: Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Dehradun.

Email ✉: Sagarkapil211@gmail.com

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times through different blood sampling, making it impossible to calculate the diabetes prevalence.(2) According to recent 8 edition of international diabetes federation (IDF) Diabetes Atlas 2017 diabetes is rise across the world, and about 244.9 million people suffer from this disorder which further extend to 48%by 2045.(628.6)million.(3)The WHO observed in 2016 data that the increase in weight and obesity in women leads to suffer from this metabolic syndrome.(4)Basically, on the basis of classification there are two type of diabetes i.e. Insulin dependent (type1) and Non-Insulin Dependent(type2),There is an evidence that regulation of blood glucose level reduces chances of diabetes and prevent the damage of eye, kidney and nerves. (5). Diabetes insipidus is an uncommon illness that causes frequent urination and thirst. One of the main causes of the polyuria polydipsia syndrome is diabetes insipidus, which is characterized by polydipsia of more than 3 L/d and a high hypotonic urine output mechanism. There are two basic kinds of diabetes insipidus: those with central or renal origin) as well as secondary polyuria (due to original polydipsia). Also referred to as hypothalamic or neurogenic diabetes insipidus. Central diabetes insipidus is a condition that due to insufficient synthesis and production of arginine vasopressin. (AVP) in the neurohypophyseal system of the hypothalamus in response to osmotic stimulation. The majority of cases are caused by illnesses that interfere with neurohypophysis. (6) Majorly, (T2DM) accounts for more than 90% of instances of diabetic mellitus. Still, Diabetes mellitus forms are frequently not differentiated in estimations at the

population level; as a result, in this Review, all forms of diabetes are referred to as diabetes mellitus, unless otherwise noted. Despite the genetic, An individual's architecture may determine reaction to modifications in the surroundings the primary motivators of the T2DM pandemic worldwide are the increases in obesity, a population that is sedentary, consumes foods high in calories, and ageing.(7)

Over the past three decades, diabetes mellitus has tripled in frequency globally, ranking as the ninth largest cause of death. Type 2 diabetes accounts for 90% of all occurrences of diabetes, which affects around one in eleven people worldwide. China and India are the main epicentres of the rapidly spreading worldwide T2DM epidemic, which is mostly an Asian problem. Mostly Genetic factors contributes to individual susceptibility to T2DM, an unhealthy diet and sedentary lifestyle are significant drivers of the current global epidemic; early developmental factors (such as intrauterine exposures) also influence susceptibility to T2DM later in life. Some cases of T2DM could be prevented with lifestyle adjustments, such as keeping a healthy body weight, eating a healthy diet and keep body fit by doing regular exercise and daily walk for at least 10,000 feet. Cardiovascular problems account for the majority of complications experienced by people with type 2 diabetes, and are the primary cause of morbidity and death in this patient population. An updated perspective on the global epidemiology of type 2 diabetes (T2DM), together with dietary, lifestyle, and other risk factors for T2DM and its consequences, are provided by this review.(8)

Insulin resistance and β -cell dysfunction are the two primary signs of diabetes mellitus (T2DM), which are caused by a disturbance in homeostasis. A vicious trio of β -cell failure (~80% of their β -cell activity) and insulin resistance in the muscles and liver is the main source of physiological issues. Although T2DM is often thought to be an insulin resistance and deficiency issue, recent studies on the disease's biology suggest that other significant components may also play a role in insulin shortage and associated functional impairment. The pancreatic islet is composed of β -cells (48–59%) that release insulin, α -cells (33–46%) that release glucagon, δ -cells that produce somatostatin, and F cells that release polypeptides in a similar proportion. Additionally, paracrine interactions take place in the order of β -cell to α -cells followed by delta cells and polypeptide cell. Although β -cell interactions are currently the focus, other pancreatic cell interactions are also very important and require further investigation to fully understand their involvement in glucose homeostasis. Furthermore, fat cells (accelerated lipolysis), the gastrointestinal tract (incretin deficiency/resistance), α -cells (hyperglucagonemia), the kidneys (increased glucose reabsorption), the brain (insulin resistance), and the intricate interactions that take place between these factors and T2DM associated genes all play a significant role in the development of glucose resistance in T2DM (9).

Mechanism involves in type 1 Diabetes mellitus

Type 1 diabetes is a chronic autoimmune disorder, characterized by T lymphocytes attacking insulin-producing beta cells. Previous clinical trials have found that continued Immune suppression temporarily reduces the Insulin production. Preclinical investigations indicated that a monoclonal antibody targeting CD3 may reverse Hyperglycaemia upon presentation induces tolerance a recurring sickness. Antibody treatment basically decrease the glycosylated haemoglobin level. Basically type 1 diabetes is insulin dependent diabetes. (10)

Autoimmune Destruction

The main mechanism involve in T1DM is that immune system of body automatically target or deplete the beta cells. This destruction is mediated primarily by autoreactive T cells, which are part of the normal immune repertoire. And further these T cells target the beta cells, leading to their subsequent loss or inability to produce insulin. (11)

Genetics

Type 1 diabetes usually affects people without a family history of the condition. Of patients, only 10 to 15 percent had a first- or second-degree family with the disease. About 50% of monozygotic twins, 5% of siblings, and 6% of

children develop type 1 diabetes, compared to the 0.4% prevalence in the general population. Accordingly, family members of sufferers are far more likely to get type 1 diabetes throughout their lives. Over 50% of people with type 1 diabetes are genetically at risk, according to meta-analyses and genome-wide association studies. The bulk of the genes that predispose to type 1 diabetes are located on chromosome 6 in the Major Histocompatibility Complex (MHC) area, sometimes referred to as HLA (Human Leucocyte Antigen). Between 40 and 50 percent of the hereditary risk for type 1 diabetes is occur by polymorphic alleles in HLA complex. (12)

Consequences of beta cell loss

Due to the beta cell destruction, the regulation of blood glucose level impaired. This lead to hyperglycaemia which is an indication of diabetes. This affect the alfa cell also which secrete glucagon and make complication in glucose homeostasis and contributing the metabolic dysregulation seen T1DM. (13)

A new era of immunotherapies for people with type 1 diabetes

In contrast to previous widely immunosuppressive regimens, more sophisticated therapies have been developed in the last 20 years to treat autoimmune and inflammatory diseases. Examples of these therapies include rituximab and anti-tumor necrosis factor [TNF] therapy for rheumatoid arthritis, which have more limited side effects. Applying this idea to T1D, a paradigm change in the field's development of T1D immunotherapy toward the targeting of islet-specific immune pathways involved in tolerance has resulted in the creation of treatments that have the potential to prevent or reverse the disease while avoiding the toxicities of earlier immunosuppressive methods. As a result, The field has been testing these

medications in high-risk and new-onset situations for the past ten years in order to determine the biomarker of C-peptide preservation. (14)

Targeting T cell

T1D patients are presently undergoing testing for more targeted and less harmful T cell-directed treatments, which appear promising. First created in the mid-1980s as a modified version of OKT3, the first authorized monoclonal antibody used to treat acute kidney allograft rejection, targeted CD3 blockage started with an engineered, humanized antibody. However, the cytokine storm that was brought on by the drug's early mAb-activating qualities and subsequent immunogenicity resulted in serious adverse effects. In order to minimize T cell activation and immunogenicity, a mutant human Fc receptor was used in the development of teplizumab (hOKT3g [Ala-Ala]), a modified humanized variant of the antibody. Teplizumab was demonstrated to overcome kidney transplant rejection in 1995 small pilot research in a manner comparable to the parent OKT3 mAb without the previously mentioned side effects. A brief course of anti-CD3 mAb was also discovered to be able to produce a long-term remission of autoimmune diabetes in NOD mice in preclinical research conducted in the 1990s . This discovery laid the groundwork for the translation of anti-CD3 mAb into T1D. After just one 2-week course of treatment, individuals with newly diagnosed T1D demonstrated clinical safety and effectiveness of teplizumab, almost 7 years after the drug's original development. One possible explanation for the medication treatment's limitations (most patients' condition did not improve) might be a low initial beta cell mass. A phase 3 trial is now being conducted to see if teplizumab may change the course of the disease considerably in the new-onset situation. Patients treated with oteplizumab, a related monoclonal antibody, showed results in early phase 2 studies that showed intact b cell

function ; nevertheless, because of the mAb's immunosuppressive and cytokine-activating characteristics, there was an increased risk of EBV reactivation. In the DEFEND-1 and DEFEND-2 phase 3 trials , follow-up studies utilizing lower dosages were unable to achieve main objectives of retained C peptide, and no registered clinical trials are presently being conducted. Minimal dosage While less selective than anti-CD3 medicines like teplizumab, ATG is another T cell strategy being tested for T1D prevention and reversal. Since ATG is produced by immunizing rabbits with human thymocytes, it is a pure rabbit sera with cytotoxic IgG antibodies directed against human T cells. As a result, it does not target a specific epitope, and repeated exposures may raise the risk of serum sickness.(15)

Human K⁺ channel Kv1.3 regulates membrane potential and Ca²⁺ signaling in T cells; its expression is four to five times higher in memory and activated CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells, especially Tem cells. Since Kv1.3 becomes the main functional K⁺ channel and is upregulated to 1500–2000 channels per cell in activated stem cells (CD45RA[–]/CCR7), it has been recognized as a potential signature biomarker in these cells. Kv1.3 is highly expressed in the parenchyma of demyelinated MS lesions, perivenular infiltrates, and post-mortem MS brain inflammatory infiltrates. Kv1.3⁺ cells are composed of CCR7[–] CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ Tem cells, confirming earlier studies that demonstrated activated memory T cells constitute an essential part of MS lesions in the brain. In both RA and T1D, illness-associated autoreactive T cells mostly have a high Kv1.3 expression profile. It has been demonstrated that autoreactive Tem cells from RA and T1D patients preferentially block the synthesis and proliferation of cytokines by small-molecule Kv1.3 inhibitors in vitro. Furthermore, in rat models of RA and T1D, these inhibitors were shown to enhance

autoimmunity without resulting in systemic harm.(16)

Kv1.3Channel inhibitor-

Membrane potential, like T cells, is controlled by the Kv1.3 k⁺ channel in humans, and its expression is fourfold to fivefold higher in activated and memory CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells, particularly Tem cells. In activated Tem cells (CD45RA[–]/CCR7), Kv1.3 increases to 1500-2000 channels per cell and becomes the primary functional K⁺ channel, making it a potential biomarker. Kv1.3 is highly expressed in postmortem multiple sclerosis (MS) brain inflammatory infiltrates, as well as in perivenular infiltrates and demyelinated MS lesion parenchyma.Kv1.3⁺ cells are CCR7[–] CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ Tem cells, indicating the presence of activated memory T cells in MS brain lesions, as previously discovered. Similarly, in both RA and T1D, disease-associated autoreactive T cells are mainly Tem, with high Kv1.3 expression. Small-molecule Kv1.3 inhibitors were discovered to specifically decrease cytokine generation and proliferation of autoreactive Tem cell from RA and T1D patient in vitro and improved immunity. There were no evidence of systemic toxicity in rat models of RA and T1D.(17)

Type 2 Diabetes mellitus-

Insulin resistance, a disorder in which cells do not use insulin as it should, can occasionally be paired with a complete lack of insulin to cause type 2 diabetes mellitus. Other names for it include adult-onset diabetes and non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. Approx 90% cases of diabetes are type 2 diabetes caused by -

- Abnormality in gluco-receptor of beta cell so they respond at higher level of glucose.
- Reduced sensitivity of peripheral tissue to insulin receptor.

- Excess hyperglycaemic hormone or over excess production of glucagon.

Factor affecting type 2 diabetes mellitus-

Age

The terms "adult onset" and "maturity-onset" have been used for many years to describe type 2 diabetes, indicating that the condition is more common as people age. Of the total population 65 years of age and older, 18.4% have diabetes. One at 75 years of age or older, several polls indicate a plateauing or mild deterioration.⁶ Noteworthy, a significant cut-off point for determining the prevalence of diabetes has historically been set at 45 years of age. However, type 2 diabetes has shockingly increased by 70% in younger individuals (ages 30-39) over the past eight years. One Rates increased by a sharp 40% for the 40–49 age range. Current lifestyle trends are responsible for these shocking numbers, which lead to increase excess.

GESTATIONAL DIABETES MELLITUS (GDM)

Gestational diabetes is defined as any degree of intolerance of glucose that occur or is first recognized during pregnancy. GDM affects around 4% of all pregnancies in the United States, but the range varies greatly (1-14%) according on the racial or ethnic groups analysed, as well as the frequency of obesity. Increased screening and detection rates, as well as the trend of older women having children, may contribute to the development of GDM to diabetes. In the Nurses' Health Study, pregravid factors of GDM were investigated. The following factors were identified to indicate a woman's risk for GDM: cigarette smoking, weight increase in early adulthood, advanced maternal age, non-white ethnicity, higher BMI, and family history of diabetes. There

are differences in the rates at which GDM progresses to diabetes; the risk of type 2 diabetes increases from 5% in the first three to six months after giving birth to 47% at the 5-year mark.¹⁵ Review of other research showed that women with previous GDM had a 40% chance of developing diabetes at age of 15. According to high-risk ethnic groups, 50% of women develop diabetes within five years, indicating that ethnicity has a significant impact on the development of diabetes following a GDM pregnancy. Of fact, these ethnic groups' stated rates of obesity and physical inactivity also serve as confounding variables that are reported in all the women that affect the progression in diabetes. (18)

(IFG) AND (IGT)

IFG and IGT act as median in normal glycemia and diabetes. IFG criteria include those with fasting blood glucose levels between 110 and 125 mg/dl. An oral glucose tolerance test value of ≥ 140 mg/dl but 200 mg/dl after two hours is used to calculate IGT. IGT patients have normal glycemic levels for the majority of their life; glucose tolerance testing is the only way to identify the metabolic abnormality. Particularly among non-white racial and cultural groups, IGT suggests an elevated risk of type 2 diabetes development, ranging from 2.3 to 11% annually. Women are more likely to be in each minority group. Diabetes etiology is directly impacted by insulin resistance and the ensuing IGT. According to data from six prospective studies involving a variety of groups, increased fasting and 2-hour post-challenge glucose levels were the most reliable indicators of the transition from IGT to type 2 diabetes. The identification of IGT is very important since it is a substantial risk factor for type 2 diabetes and indicates chronic insulin resistance.⁽¹⁹⁾

Lifestyle factor correlation

Type 2 diabetes is largely caused by lifestyle factors, such as smoking, alcohol use, physical inactivity, and sedentary behavior. The most important risk factor for type 2 diabetes has been shown to be obesity, which may influence insulin resistance and the course of the illness. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2011) estimates that around 90% of people with diabetes develop type 2 diabetes, which is mostly brought on by obesity. Moreover, obesity has a strong genetic component. Many overweight and obese people suffer from obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), a treatable sleep disorder that has been found to be a distinct, modifiable risk factor for insulin resistance and glucose intolerance. People who have healthy lifestyles that include eating a balanced diet, exercising frequently, and keeping their weight in check have a decreased incidence of hyperglycemia, according to studies. In particular, the risk of diabetes might increase by up to 89% when these low-risk behaviors are absent. Numerous studies have shown that OSA is much more prevalent in T2DM patients (36%–60%) than in the general population. Diet is also thought to be a significant determinant for type 2 diabetes.

Gut metagenome correlation

The gut metagenome has been implicated in the development of type 2 diabetes in a few recent investigations. Bacterial chemotaxis, flagellar assembly, butyrate biosynthesis, and cofactor and vitamin metabolism are all reduced in type 2 diabetic patients, while membrane transport of sugars, methane metabolism, branched-chain amino acid (BCAA) transport, xenobiotic degradation and metabolism, and sulphate reduction are all increased. Seven of the T2DM-enriched KEGG orthologues' indicators were connected to oxidative stress resistance, per a research. Among these indications were glutathione reductase (NADPH) (K00383), nitric

oxide reductase (K02448), catalase (K03781), peroxiredoxin (K03386), cytochrome c peroxidase (K00428), putative iron-dependent peroxidase (K07223), Mn-containing catalase (K07217), and k00383 measures. The gut microbiota of individuals with type 2 diabetes shows a reduction in butyrate bA, flagellar assembly, and bacterial chemotaxis. By comparing the T2DM score with the proportion of T2DM patients, the gut microbiota-based T2D classifier approach correctly categorizes individuals with type 2 diabetes. For example, "functional dysbiosis" rather than a specific microbial species may be the cause of dysbiosis in T2DM patients, while bacteria that produce butyrate may provide protection against many illnesses. Gut metagenomic indicators show more specificity in distinguishing between T2DM patients and controls based on human genome variation, indicating that they might be a useful supplementary technique to monitor gut health for determining the risk of the illness. (20)

Stress and lack of sleep

Compared to males, women are more negatively impacted by discrimination and PTSD in terms of their sleep quality. A study of epidemiological research by sex revealed that women of all ages were 40% more likely to have insomnia. Loss of sleep, short sleep duration, and poor sleep quality were then linked to obesity and, to a greater extent, to impaired glucose metabolism brought on by insulin resistance. Short sleep duration (less than five hours) and trouble falling or staying asleep were linked to increased risk for diabetes in a meta-analysis. After sex-based stratification, however, similar impact estimates were reported in both sexes. In a smaller prospective research with sex differences as the main outcome, sleep deprivation increased food and fat consumption, but men were more likely to gain weight due to

higher daily calorie intake, particularly at night. According to the findings of a meta-analysis of observational studies that included sex-specific subgroup analysis, shift employment was linked to an increased risk of diabetes in males. There are often conflicting findings about the effects of shift work, work stress, and coping that relate to sex and gender differences.(21)

Foetal Programming/Epigenetics in Animals

Since there are few studies on the impact of epigenetics on the risk of diabetes in humans, we mostly depend on research conducted on rodents. There is proof that maternal undernutrition or hyperglycemia, in an epigenetic way, causes sex-specific intragenerational transfer of glucose tolerance and fat distribution from one generation to the next. In mice, obesity exclusively progresses down the maternal line, but IGT was passed down through both parental lineages. Birth weight loss only manifests when it is passed down from the F1 to the F2 generation via the paternal line. However, in a different investigation, it was discovered that defective glucose-tolerant paternal lines significantly increased the birth weight of F2. Offspring of mice fed a high-fat diet (HFD) showed sex variations in glucose metabolism. Compared to female mice, male progeny in the HFD group had reduced insulin content, islet area, and insulin production, as well as higher oxidative stress. Compared to male offspring, female mice whose moms were fed a regulated diet had reduced levels of estrogen. One possible explanation for the sex difference is that male beta cells experience greater levels of oxidative stress, which is linked to lower amounts of estradiol and may result in a loss of beta cell protection. IGT was previously shown in both male and female offspring of obese mice during gestation and lactation in overfed animals. Male offspring of fat moms had similar abnormalities, including reduced pancreatic insulin concentration. Additionally, among the

category of fat descendants regardless of sex, insulin levels were greater than in the control animal group.(22)

Pathophysiology of hyperglycaemia in T2DM

Insulin release from the pancreatic β -cells typically enhances the absorption of glucose by skeletal muscle and adipose tissue while decreasing the liver's production of glucose. Hyperglycaemia, or an excess of glucose in the blood, arises when β -cell failure in the pancreas and/or insulin resistance in the liver, skeletal muscle, or adipose tissue take place. The several elements mentioned at the top have an impact on insulin action and secretion in type 2 diabetes mellitus. Elevated free fatty acid and proinflammatory cytokines contribute to insulin resistance, while excessive glucagon secretion further elevates blood glucose level. Chronic hyperglycaemia can induce oxidative stress, resulting in complication such as neuropathy and cardiovascular disease. Effective management is crucial to mitigate these risk. (23)

Mechanisms leading to β -Cell Dysfunction-;

Hyperglycaemia and hyperlipidaemia are frequently present in an over nutrition condition, which favours IR and chronic inflammation, much like in obesity. Because of differences in their inherited sensitivity, β -cells are vulnerable to toxic stimuli such inflammation, inflammatory stress, ER stress, metabolic/oxidative stress, and amyloid stress, which can result in a loss of islet integrity. β -cells are harmed by the metabolic and oxidative stress brought on by lipotoxicity, glucotoxicity, and glucolipotoxicity in obesity. There are several ways that stress caused by high saturated FFA levels might activate the UPR pathway, including by directly disrupting ER homeostasis, activating IP3 receptors, or inhibiting the sarco/endoplasmic reticulum Ca^{2+} ATPase (SERCA), which is

responsible for ER Ca^{2+} mobilization. Additionally, chronically high glucose levels speed up the β -cells' synthesis of proinsulin and islet amyloid polypeptides (IAAP), which leads to the accumulation of misfolded insulin and IAAP and increases the creation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) through oxidative protein folding. In addition to promoting proapoptotic signals, proinsulin mRNA degradation, and the generation of interleukin (IL)-1 β , which draws macrophages and heightens local islet inflammation, these activities alter the mobilization of normal ER Ca^{2+} . As mentioned before, insulin production needs to be strictly regulated in order to precisely meet metabolic demand. Enough islet integrity must be maintained for β -cells to react to metabolic demands. In pathological conditions, the aforementioned mechanism may ultimately

lead to disruption of the integrity and organization of the islets, hinder the best possible cell-to-cell communication within the pancreatic islets, insufficiently regulate the release of insulin and glucagon, and worsen hyperglycemia. Insulin secretory dysfunction is the primary cause of β -cell failure and the root cause of type 2 diabetes. It can be brought on by abnormalities in the secretion process or by flaws in the synthesis of insulin or any of its precursors. For instance, the downstream signaling cascade would be impacted by reduced expression of the GLUT2 glucose transporter, and proinsulin folding failure is another result that is commonly linked to diabetes and insufficient insulin production.(24)

Hormonal regulation-

Treatment and prevention of type 2 Diabetes mellitus

Management of type 2 diabetes mellitus involves a combination of lifestyle changes and medication. A heart-healthy, low-carb diet, exercise, weight loss, and the use of oral or injectable anti-diabetic medications are all part of the therapy of hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetes. Anti-hyperglycaemic therapies include substances that facilitate insulin production, such as meglitinides

and sulfonylureas, or that improve insulin availability (either by administering insulin injections, or indirectly through the incretin pathway, including glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors), enhance insulin sensitivity. Biguanide, thiazolidinediones, or sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors that make urine more excretory of glucose. There are agents that operate through many mechanisms. It might be difficult to navigate this lengthy list of anti-hyperglycemic medications for doctors. Providers treating

patients with type 2 diabetes must be well-versed on the particular hazards and advantages of each drug class and its constituent agents as treatment should be tailored to each patient's specific circumstances.(25)

Class	Medication/therapies in class	Primary physiological action	Advantages	Disadvantages/Adverse effect	Efficacy
DPP-inhibitor	-Sitagliptin -Vildagliptin -Saxagliptin -Linagliptin -Alogliptin	-Increase secretion. -Decreases Glucagon secretion.	-No hyperglycemia. -weight neutral. -Well tolerated.	↑risk for DKA Rare urticaria/angioedema.	Intermediate
Sulfonyl urea	- Glibenclamide -Glipizide -Glimipiride -Glyburide	-Increase insulin secretion	-Extensive Experience. -Decrease microvascular risk. -Inexpensive.	-Hypoglycemia. -↑ in weight. -Uncertain cardiovascular safety.	High
Thiazolidinedione (TZDs)	-Pioglitazone - Rosiglitazone	-Increase insulin sensitivity	-low risk for Hypoglycemia -Durability. -↑HDL-C ↓Triacylglycerol.	-↑in weight. -Bone loss -Edema/heart failure.	High
Meglitinides	- Repaglinide. -Nateglinide	-↑insulin secretion	-Lower cost -↓postprandial glucose excursion.	Hypoglycaemia ↑in weight. Uncertain cardiovascular safety. Frequent dosing schedule.	Intermediate-High
α-glucosidase inhibitor	Acarbose Miglitol	Slow carbohydrate absorption and digestion	-low risk of hyperglycemia -↓postprandial glucose excursion. Cardiovascular safety. -Lower costs.	-Frequent GI side effect. -frequent dosing schedule. -Dose adjustment/avoidance for renal diseases.	Low-intermediate
Bile acid sequestrant	Colesevelam	↓hepatic glucose production. ↑incretin level.	Lower cost. No hypoglycaemia ↓ LDL level	Constipation ↑Triacylglycerol. May decrease absorption of other medication.	Low - intermediate

Overcome insulin resistance

(a) Biguanides

Biguanide (metformin) was the first line oral treatment in management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Basically, biguanides decrease hepatic gluconeogenesis and improve insulin sensitivity by increasing the peripheral utilisation of blood glucose. Biguanide is the drug that do not act on pancreatic beta cell. It also has additional activity that lower the serum fatty acid concentration. Phenformin banned in india due to higher risk of lactic acidosis. Metformin is contraindicated in renal insufficiency because lactic acidosis.

Benefits- An efficient anti-hyperglycemic medication, metformin lowers hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) by 1% to 2%. It is weight-neutral or offers a slight weight loss, has a long-term safety profile, is inexpensive, and does not raise the risk of hypoglycemia. Metformin has no negative effects on the cardiovascular system (CV). Conversely, in other groups, it seems to lower the risk of CV events. For any diabetes-related outcome (including both macrovascular and microvascular problems), metformin significantly decreased risk by 32%, 42% for compared to the group receiving insulin or sulfonylurea, and 36% for all-cause mortality and diabetes-related death. Additionally, metformin was more effective than intensive treatment with insulin or a sulfonylurea

in reducing all-cause mortality and any diabetes-related endpoints ($p = 0.003$).

Adverse Effects and Precautions- It may cause stomach discomfort, vitamin B6 insufficiency, and hyperlactatemia with metabolic acidosis. Metformin should be avoided in people at risk of lactic acidosis, such as having a previous history of metformin-induced lactic acidosis, severely compromised renal function, advanced liver disease, unstable heart failure, hemodynamic instability, baseline metabolic acidosis, or substantial alcohol use. Metformin is renally eliminated; hence it should be avoided if creatinine clearance is less than 30 mL/min/1.73 m². Metformin is often not contraindicated for individuals with stable compensated heart failure (HF). (26)

(b) Thiazolidinedione

These are PPAR γ activator which bind to the nuclear PPAR γ which in turn activate the insulin-responsiveness gene that regulate carbohydrate and lipid metabolism and sensitize peripheral tissue to insulin that reduce blood glucose level by-

- Increasing the glucose transport into muscles and adipose tissue .
- Promoting lipogenesis.

- Inhibiting hepatic gluconeogenesis.

Drugs like Pioglitazone and Rosiglitazone, Troglitazone etc., are used. Rosiglitazone banned in India due to the risk of myocardial infarction, CHF, stroke and death.

Adverse Effects: Cardiovascular defects, rarely hepatic dysfunction, plasma volume expansion and weight gain are observed. (27)

Enhanced Insulin Secretion

These are drugs that enhanced the insulin secretion by acting on pancreatic beta cell.

(a) Sulfonyl ureas/ glinides

Despite being well-established for decades, sulfonylurea medication includes a risk of hypoglycaemia, particularly in older and multimorbid patients. Holstein et al. (39) reported in population-based research conducted in Germany that, depending on the specific sulfonylurea medication used, there were between 0.9 and 5.6 severe hypoglycaemia events per 1000 patient-years. These medicines also encourage weight gain. Some (not yet clear) evidence that sulfonylureas are linked to a greater cardiovascular risk than metformin has also been found in observational studies. It also appears that both medications lose their effectiveness more quickly than metformin (e5). Repaglinide can also be utilized in individuals with severe renal insufficiency since it has a similar side-effect profile as sulfonylureas but a shorter half-life. (28) Sulfonyl urea second generation are more potent than first generation. Gliclazide has additional antiplatelet action. These are K^+ channel blocker drugs. Drug act on sulfonyl urea receptor on pancreatic beta cell membrane that inhibit ATP sensitive K^+ channel which enhance the Ca^{++} influx that led to depolarisation of pancreatic beta cell

that improve the insulin secretion. Newer sulfonyl urea are 20 to 50 times more potent on milligram basis and have prolonged duration of action. Chlorpropamide has longer $t_{1/2}$ -30-36 hours. And glyburide has maximum insulin tropic action whereas tolbutamide has least.

Mechanism of action – Drug acting on the sulfonyl urea receptor on pancreatic beta cell membrane which inhibit K^+ channel and enhance the Ca^{++} influx that lead to depolarisation of beta cell and result in insulin secretion.

Adverse effect- Hypoglycaemia, weight gain, hypersensitivity, teratogenic in nature. (29)

(b) Glinides

An insulin secretagogue called repaglinide helps people with type 2 diabetes by lowering their blood glucose levels. Repaglinide reduces fasting and postprandial hyperglycemia, as well as the quantity of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), in people with type 2 diabetes, according to recent studies. Compared to glitazones, metformin, or sulphonylureas, repaglinide lower HbA1c. It is equally effective when taken in conjunction with other drugs as any other combination. Repaglinide has been shown to have a higher effect on postprandial glycemia than comparators. Its tendency to induce hypoglycemia is comparable to or somewhat less than that of sulphonylureas. Compared with glitazones and sulphonylureas, repaglinide produces less weight gain. When metformin is unable to effectively control blood glucose levels, when flexible dosing is necessary (for instance, in the elderly or during Ramadan fasting), when lowering postprandial glucose is specifically desired, or when metformin cannot be used due to side effects, repaglinide can be used to treat type 2 diabetes. Repaglinide may also be helpful when diabetics with renal impairment need an oral treatment. Because of its short half-life,

repaglinide should be taken before each meal, usually three times a day. It can be used by patients with mild to severe renal impairment at different phases of the illness. Even though the drug has been the subject of several clinical trials and observational studies, its worldwide usage is still far lower than that of, instance, sulphonylureas. The potential of repaglinide to lower blood glucose levels in individuals with type 2 diabetes has not yet been fully acknowledged by many physicians.(30)

Miscellaneous drugs

(a) DPP-4 Inhibitor (Dipeptidyl Peptidase.)

By reducing blood DPP4 activity by 80%, DPP-4 inhibitors lessen the breakdown of glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptides, GLP-1, and incretin hormones. This makes more endogenous incretins available, which promotes the release of insulin. inhibits the release of glucagon from pancreatic α -cells in a way that is reliant on glucose. These drugs come in single-pill or extended-release versions and can be used either by itself or in combination with metformin. Pioglitazone can also be purchased with alogliptin, a DPP-4 inhibitor. According to a meta-analysis of 80 randomized controlled trials, DPP-4 inhibitors reduced mean HbA1c by 0.6% to 1.1% (without adjustment). For comparisons of placebos, blinding, or background treatment. DPP-4 inhibitors demonstrated modest systolic and diastolic blood pressure lowering benefits when compared to placebos or no therapy, according to a meta-analysis of 15 randomized controlled trials. Changes in body weight do not alter these agents. Alogliptin, sitagliptin, and saxagliptin did not enhance cardiovascular outcomes or raise the risk of MACE, according to prospective cardiovascular outcomes studies. Studies on linagliptin are still ongoing. With minimal chance of hypoglycemia (unless used in conjunction with insulin or insulin

secretagogues), DPP-4 inhibitors are generally well-tolerated and safe. One side effect that is commonly mentioned is nasopharyngitis. Serious hypersensitivity events, including anaphylaxis, angioedema, and exfoliative skin reactions, have been linked to this medication class. Treatment with these inhibitors should be discontinued immediately if pancreatitis is suspected. Because the majority of DPP-4 inhibitors are eliminated from the body through the kidneys, dose changes are required when using sitagliptin, saxagliptin, or alogliptin to treat patients with moderate to severe renal impairment. Individuals with renal impairment do not require dosage modifications since the bulk of linagliptin's clearance occurs through nonrenal mechanisms.(31)

(b) Sodium Glucose Cotransporter 2 Inhibitors

SGLT2 inhibitors work by targeting the kidney to reduce hyperglycemia and encourage the elimination of glucose through the urine. In the proximal tubule, renal reabsorption of glucose is primarily controlled by the SGLT2 and the glucose transport protein SGLT2. There is proof that SGLT2 expression is elevated in type 2 diabetics, which improves glucose reabsorption and keeps blood glucose levels up. By promoting the excretion of glucose in the urine, SGLT2 inhibition reduces the renal ability to reabsorb glucose by about 30% to 50%, hence lowering hyperglycaemia. Because SGLT2 inhibitors don't rely on insulin to work, they can be used at any point throughout the course of the disease and in combination with any kind of glucose-lowering drug. This covers those patients who have had the disease for a long time and have low insulin secretion. There are combinations of SGLT2 inhibitor and DPP-4 inhibitor, such dapagliflozin and saxagliptin and empagliflozin and linagliptin⁴⁵, as well as SGLT2 inhibitor and

metformin in single dose. When compared to placebo, SGLT2 inhibitor medication lowers HbA1c by about 0.69% (95% CI, 0.75 to 0.62), body weight by about 2.1 kg (95% CI, 2.3 to 2.0), and systolic blood pressure by about 3.9 mm Hg (95% CI, 4.6 to 3.3) on average. There was no information available on the effect of SGLT2 inhibitors on cardiovascular events prior to the publication of data from the Empagliflozin Cardiovascular Outcome Event Trial in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients Removing Excess Glucose trial in 2015. In the United States, however, SGLT2 inhibitors are not recommended for use if eGFR is less than 45 mL/min/1.73 m² (empagliflozin or canagliflozin) or less than 60 mL/min/1.73 m² (dapagliflozin). This is because the effectiveness of these medications depends on renal function.(32)

Combined effect of Dapagliflozin/sitagliptin and metformin on public health

Chronic kidney disease is often the outcome of type 2 diabetes. It has been estimated that 22% of patients with T2DM have moderate or severe renal insufficiency (estimated glomerular filtration rate [eGFR]<60 ml/min/1.73 ml CKD Stages 3–5), while 38% of patients have mild renal insufficiency (eGFR ≥60 and <90 mL/min/1.73 m², Stage 2). Type 2 diabetes is more common in people 65 and older; 43% of those with the disease had moderate or severe renal insufficiency, and 48% have mild renal insufficiency. While it is majorly accepted while choosing an antihyperglycemic medication (AHA) to treat type 2 diabetes renal function should be considered first to prevent adverse effect, only CKD Stages 3–5 is frequently considered relevant to that decision. So, combining dapagliflozin, metformin, and sitagliptin offer several advantages for managing type 2 Diabetes mellitus-

- **Comprehensive Glycaemic control-** Dapagliflozin reduce glucose reabsorption in the kidney, metformin decreases liver glucose production and sitagliptin enhance insulin secretion leading to improved blood sugar level.
- **Weight Management** – Dapagliflozin promote weight loss which will be beneficial for obese patient.
- **Cardiovascular and renal benefit** – This combination may lower the risk of cardiovascular event and kidney progression.
- **Reduced risk of Hypoglycaemia-** The combine mechanism minimises the likelihood of low blood sugar level episode.

Sitagliptin medication improved glycemic control more than dapagliflozin and was usually well tolerated in individuals with type 2 diabetes, moderate renal insufficiency, and insufficient glycemic control on metformin ± sulfonylurea. (33) In each therapy group, the mean baseline HbA1c was around 9% (75 mmol/mol). The difference between DAPA + SITA + MET ER (-1.73% [- 19.0 mmol/mol]) and SITA + MET SR (-1.28% [- 14.1 mmol/mol]; difference of -0.46% [- 5.1 mmol/mol], $p < 0.001$) and DAPA + MET ER (-1.33% [- 14.6 mmol/mol]; difference -0.4% [4.4 mmol/mol], at week 16, was significantly higher than the adjusted mean reduction in HbA1c from baseline. Similarly, DAPA + SITA + MET ER substantially reduced HbA1c from baseline at week 12 compared to SITA + MET SR ($p = 0.0006$) and DAPA + MET ER ($p = 0.0276$). When compared to DAPA + MET ER, DAPA + SITA + MET ER significantly decreased postprandial blood glucose at week 16 ($p = 0.0394$), and it significantly decreased fasting blood glucose when compared to SITA + MET SR ($p = 0.0226$). In comparison to SITA + MET SR (12.8%) ($p < 0.001$) and DAPA + MET ER (21.3%) ($p =$

0.0023), the percentage of patients who achieved HbA1c < 7.0% (53 mmol/mol) at week 16 was substantially greater with DAPA + SITA + MET ER (38.5%). Every trial drug was well tolerated. So at last Triple FDC of DAPA + SITA + MET ER tablets once day achieved considerably better glycemic control than dual combination once daily in individuals with type 2 diabetes inadequately managed with metformin, with no apparent safety issues.(34)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Insulin resistance or insufficient insulin synthesis are the main causes of high blood glucose levels in diabetes mellitus (DM), a chronic illness. A diversified strategy is needed for its care, involving medication, lifestyle changes, and continuous observation. Key complications that can result in serious health problems including blindness and kidney failure are diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy. The benefit of more recent treatments, such as SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 agonists, in lowering the cardiovascular risks connected to DM has been highlighted by recent research. Improving results and avoiding complications need patient involvement and education. The Baker Heart and Diabetes Institute's researchers have created a technique to use FDA-approved cancer medications to regenerate insulin-producing cells, which might lessen insulin reliance in people with type 1 diabetes. This is one recent development in the treatment of diabetes.

- **Teplizumab approval-** This drug has been approved as the first diseases-modifying therapy for type diabetes, showing promise in preserving beta –cell function in newly diagnosed patient.
- **Artificial Pancreas-** New automated systems are being developed that can continuously monitor glucose and adjust insulin delivery

without user input, enhancing diabetes Management.

These innovation signal significant progress towards improving diabetes care and management. Combination medicine (Dapagliflozin + sitagliptin +metformin) have good therapeutic action in glycaemic control in type 2 Diabetes mellitus administered orally.

CONCLUSION

Irregular production of insulin as well as resistance of insulin are the indication of diabetes mellitus, a chronic disorder that causes ↑ in blood sugar level known as Hyperglycemia. Because of its increasing worldwide prevalence, immediate action is required. Dietary and physical activity changes are key components of effective treatment, and medication is used as required. Early detection and intensive glycemic control can mitigate complication such as cardiovascular diseases and microvascular issues. Education on self- management is crucial for improving patient outcome and improvement of life. Ultimately, a multifaceted approach targeting both glycemic control and overall health is essential to combat this epidemic situation.

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